

MANUFACTURE WITH SPREAD TOW FIBER MATERIALS FOR REDUCED MICRO-CRACKING

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ABSTRACT

The recent carbon fibers, with fiber architecture of the spread tow type, has shown radical improvements in critical material properties during use in the ongoing EU project CHATT (Cryogenic Hypersonic Advanced Tank Technologies), especially for the strain at onset of micro-cracking, transverse to the fiber direction. Liquid composite manufacture (wet filament winding, RTM) has been used in CHATT for these materials. The manufacturing challenge has been to achieve high quality and short cycle times. The processing issues have been solved using a combination of process simulation and manufacturing equipment modifications. The manufactured subscale demonstrator tubes have successfully been tested in CHATT towards the demanding loading conditions specified in the project, indicating that the TeXtreme® material performs similar to a load carrying liner material.

1 INTRODUCTION

The EU project CHATT is developing new technologies for improved fuel tanks in future space crafts [1]. NASA has a similar ongoing larger project, which has reported significant performance improvements [2].

2 SCREENING PROCESS SIMULATION

The in-house software WetWind, for process simulation of wet filament winding, was used to analyse tubes [3]. WetWind was updated with new capabilities in 2012 and was here used to rapidly analyse a large number of materials, lay-ups and special processing steps. The residual stresses after mandrel release and curing were analysed as well as the important operational temperature load.

2.1 Simplified tank specification

A simplified but demanding specification is here used for the cylindrical part of the tank, see Table 1. The allowed gas permeability leakage is in addition very low.

Operational Inner Pressure (MPa)	0.6
Burst Pressure (MPa)	1.2
¹ Minimum Temperature (°C)	-253
² Maximum Temperature (°C)	+327
Inner Radius (mm)	2920
Laminate Thickness (mm)	2.0

¹Used temperature in these calculations. The real temperature will be higher.

²Used temperature in these calculations. The real temperature will be lower.

Table 1: Simplified specification for the tank.

2.2 Studied wet filament winding concepts

The critical stress in the transverse fiber direction have here mainly been studied using process simulations, to see how much it can be affected by using a range of modifications. Many material-, layup- and manufacturing concepts for a liner less tank have been studied. Some potential conclusions were indicated by combining the calculated stresses and some judgments of the technical risk.

Mandrel Material:

The residual stresses are fairly low. The reason is that the tank is a thin-walled structure. It is however important to use a tool with low thermal expansion, to avoid stresses due to tool-composite thermal expansion mismatch. This is especially important if pitch based carbon fibers are used.

Matrix Material:

An epoxy is the likely matrix choice due to good material- and processing properties. CNT in the epoxy can significantly reduce the thermal stresses. SICOMP have done measurements on pure epoxy materials that show a reduction of the CTE from $69 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $45 \cdot 10^{-6}$ $1/^\circ\text{C}$ when 0.1 weight percent CNT is added. It is however believed that CNT might not work fully in a laminate with high fiber content and several hours before gelation. Problems with CNT leaving the matrix and moving towards the fibers can be foreseen.

Carbon Fiber:

T700 gives similar performance as T800G for the stress state at the dimensioning -253 °C temperature. Pitch fibers were initially considered as a very interesting fiber type for this application. It is however believed that the pitch fibrils might crack due to transverse stresses, since they can have less transverse strength than PAN fibrils. Blends of T800G and M65J (pitch) have also been investigated. They can theoretically suppress micro-cracks on the inside of the tank wall. The results do however indicate that the critical performance is similar to what can be achieved with PAN fiber. PAN fiber is available in more material formats and pitch fiber was hence discarded.

Manufacturing Process:

Wet Filament Winding (WFW) is the main process candidate. The reason is that it can give large fiber contents. Programmed fiber roving tension of each individual layer in the layup can also be used in this manufacturing process, to control the compaction force and stress state. Post processing in an autoclave might be needed to increase the material quality. Varied fiber tension, induction heating and shrink tape gives no significant effect on the stress state at the dimensioning -253 °C temperature. Shrink tape does however give an even fiber content and should hence potentially be used.

Pre-stress of the Inner Laminate:

A way to lower the stress state in the inner laminate at the dimensioning -253 °C, is to introduce a compression pre-stress during manufacture. This can be done by using two epoxy types in the laminate. The inner epoxy will reach gelation first. Additional cure will then create the wanted pre-stress, see Figure 1 and Figure 2. A low temperature curing epoxy ($T_g = 100$ °C) is used for the inner 1.0 mm laminate combined with a high temperature curing epoxy ($T_g = 190$ °C) for the outer 1.0 mm laminate. The net result is a lowered stress state in the inner laminate at the dimensioning -253 °C temperature with 18 %.

Figure 1: Temperature versus time at inner (node 21) -, center (node 223) - and outer (node 424) composite.

Figure 2: Cure versus time at inner (node 21) -, center (node 223) - and outer (node 424) composite.

3 WET FILAMENT WINDING WITH *HoMS*

Several combinations of the studied concepts can theoretically give improvements, but often include a large technical risk. Spread tow TeXtreme® was hence selected as the main concept, since this material behaves virtually as a load carrying liner. Spread tow material has a large potential for performance improvements in many applications. The Swedish Oxeon company pioneered the spread tow carbon fiber material 10 years ago [4]. Some measured mechanical properties are presented in Table 2 [5]. It should be observed that the effect on micro-crack initiation for thin laminae is not clearly visible for unidirectional materials. The crack propagation in laminates from thin laminae materials is much less brittle [6-8]. Improvements in the micro-crack initiation strain by a factor of 2, compared to standard carbon/epoxy roving laminate materials, have been measured by SICOMP in CHATT. This radical performance improvement was the reason why the material was selected in this project. Other material suppliers have in recent years introduced similar material types.

Property		UD composite	Plain weave laminate
Longitudinal modulus	(GPa)	138	69
Transverse modulus	(GPa)	8.1	-
In-plane shear modulus	(GPa)	-	5.5
Poisson's ratio	(-)	0.25	0.033
Longitudinal tensile strength	(MPa)	2390	1260
Longitudinal compressive strength	(MPa)	1170	709
In-plane shear strength	(MPa)	-	102

Table 2: Measured mechanical properties of TeXtreme® laminates [5].

TeXtreme® had rarely been used for wet filament winding (WFW) when the CHATT project started, according to Oxeon. Initial test tubes were hence manufactured by SICOMP. Selected winding angle was 89.8° (tangential) with 2 mm laminate thickness. The void content in the manufactured samples was measured as 5 %, which is far too high to be high quality manufacture. The problem was traced to the poor processability of TeXtreme®, regarding permeability in the thickness direction. TeXtreme® is very thin (typically 0.03-0.10 mm thick) but has a very low permeability in the thickness direction. Several ways were first tried to solve the problem including lower winding speed, higher fiber tension, apply shrink tape after winding etc. They gave no improvement. This manufacturing problem was finally solved by introducing a solution here called *HoMS* (Holes, Momentary or Stationary) in the spread tow to facilitate impregnation. The principle is described in Figure 3. The idea is to gently push the carbon fibers sideways without damaging the fibers. A roller, minute conical pins, as few pins as possible and quadratic holes spacing are used to achieve this. The pinned roller was mounted in the winding machine before the impregnation system, see Figure 4. The minute holes were hence created with the carbon fiber in dry un-impregnated material state. WFW creates immediate compaction of the fiber package at the lay down position of the mandrel. This means that the holes are primarily needed when the carbon fiber is put down on the mandrel. The holes will in fact reduce in size somewhat in the later winding process, due to strains and deformations in the material (hence it might be called momentary holes). The amount of fiber damage can be quantified by measuring the fiber fuzz collected on the pinned roller. This has been found to be negligible during manufacture at SICOMP.

Figure 3: *HoMS* principle as applied to WFW with TeXtreme®.

Figure 4: Pinned roller for improved TeXtreme® processability in SICOMPs winding machine.

Further test tubes were manufactured by SICOMP using drum impregnation and the *HoMS* procedure. The void content in the manufactured samples were measured as approximately 0 %. During manufacture of tubes with lower angles (helical winding) it was found that the achieved void content once more was too large. The problem was traced down to the lower radial compaction pressure obtained for lower winding angles. Several potential solutions were identified to increase the radial compaction pressure. The selected solution was tangential (89.8°) winding of extra T700SC carbon fiber layers to compact the TeXtreme® layers. These carbon fiber rovings are removed after winding of each layer. This solution was successfully applied to the tube manufacture. Other solutions can be derived for series production, using the same principle.

4 MANUFACTURED TUBES AND DEMONSTRATORS

Studied parameters to control the process and achieve a low void content include:

- Shrink tape.
- Release weaves.
- Winding tension.
- Winding speed.
- Impregnation systems (drum or bath type).
- New brake system for TeXtreme® winding tension control.
- Equipment adjustments.
- Pinned roller (*HoMS*).
- Use of temporary winding of $\pm 89.8^\circ$ T700SC to compact the helical TeXtreme® layers.

The tubes and demonstrators in Table 3 were manufactured. Each tube had detailed changes in the process parameters, to see how it affected the void content. Microscope pictures were taken from all test tubes, see Figure 5 to Figure 9. It was found that tube 6 and 7 gave a low void content for filament winding with $\pm 89.8^\circ$ TeXtreme®. The pinned roller in combination with drum impregnation gave here almost zero void content. Higher void contents were achieved for helical $\pm 25^\circ$ TeXtreme® winding. This was solved for tube 12, which uses temporary winding of $\pm 89.8^\circ$ to compact each full $\pm 25^\circ$ TeXtreme® layer. Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the used winding equipment.

Tube (-)	Fiber Type (-)	Lay-up (mm, °)	Laminae Thickness (mm)	Impreg. Type (-)	Type (-)
1	T700SC	2, ±55	0.5	Bath	Demonstrator
2	TeXtreme®	2, ±89.8	0.05	Drum	Test Tube
3	TeXtreme®	2, ±89.8	0.05	Drum	Test Tube
4	TeXtreme®	2, ±89.8	0.05	Drum	Test Tube
5	TeXtreme®	2, ±89.8	0.05	Drum	Test Tube
6 ²	TeXtreme®	2, ±89.8	0.05	Drum	Test Tube
7 ²	TeXtreme®	2, ±89.8	0.05	Drum	Test Tube
8	TeXtreme®	2, ±89.8	0.05	Bath	Test Tube
9	TeXtreme®	2, ±89.8	0.05	Bath	Test Tube
10 ²	TeXtreme®+T700SC	1, ±89.8 + 1, ±55	0.05 + 0.5	Drum	Demonstrator
11	TeXtreme®	2, ±25	0.05	Drum	Test Tube
12 ^{1,2}	TeXtreme®	2, ±25	0.05	Drum	Test Tube
13 ^{1,2}	TeXtreme®	2, ±25	0.05	Drum	Demonstrator

¹Carbon fibers are temporarily wound over each full ±25° TeXtreme® layer, to achieve full fiber compaction.

²Low void content with TeXtreme®.

Table 3: Manufactured test tubes and subscale demonstrator tubes.

Figure 5: Microscope picture of tube 2 laminate.

Figure 6: Microscope picture of tube 7 laminate. Low void content.

Figure 7: Microscope picture of tube 8 laminate.

Figure 8: Microscope picture of tube 11 laminate.

Figure 9: Microscope picture of tube 12 laminate. Low void content.

Figure 10: A new electrical brake system was installed to control the TeXtreme® fiber tension.

Figure 11: TeXtreme® in the drum impregnation system.

5 SUBSCALE DEMONSTRATOR

5.1 Geometry

A steel mandrel with $\varnothing_i = 145$ mm and $\varnothing_o = 165$ mm was used for manufacture. Several subscale demonstrator tubes were manufactured by filament winding, see the schematic drawing in Figure 12. These later successfully passed advanced testing (extreme temperatures, inner pressure, external load, gas permeability, etc.) towards the demanding specification, performed separately in the CHATT project. This indicates that the TeXtreme® material performs as planned and is similar to a load carrying liner material.

Figure 12: Composite subscale demonstrator.

5.2 Materials

The materials in Table 4 have been used:

- The glass weave is applied on the tubes inner surface at the tube ends (at the sealing in the test equipment). The purpose is to reduce the tubes surface roughness to enable the gas sealing to function properly.
- The glass fiber roving is used to create the outer laminate at the tube ends. The tube ends will later be machined according to Figure 12, to enable mounting of the metal flanges in the test equipment. Glass fiber was selected since it is easy to machine.

Material (-)	Position (-)	Specification (-)
¹ GF Weave	Sealing	MITEX 28 g/m ²
¹ GF Roving	Outer Laminate	Owens Corning Type 30, R25H-LS-2400, 2400 tex
Epoxy	Laminate	Huntsman LY556/HY917/DY070
TeXtreme®	Laminate	TeXtreme® 50 UD TR50S, Fiber TR50S, 0.05 mm

¹Not placed in the measured tube section.

Table 4: Used materials for manufacture of subscale demonstrator tube.

5.3 Process procedure

This procedure has been used for the subscale demonstrator tubes, see Figure 13 to Figure 15:

1. The thin glass weave is placed on to the mandrel at the tube ends.
2. Carbon fiber material is impregnated and wound on to the mandrel according to the winding program, to create the tube laminate. A separate electronic brake is used for TeXtreme®. The used impregnation system is of the drum type. The winding programs are made using a small overlap of 10 % of the band width.
3. Applied fiber tension is 20 N/roving which correspond to 36.4 MPa for TeXtreme®.
4. Glass fiber roving is wound at the tube ends using inner unspooling, bath type impregnation and a hoop ($\pm 89.8^\circ$) winding pattern.
5. A release weave is wound around the tube. The purpose is to collect excess resin and enable cure without rotation.
6. The mandrel and tube is placed in a convection oven. It is cured 4 h at 80 °C + 6 h at 140 °C, using 1 h ramp times.
7. The mandrel is released and the release weave is unwrapped.
8. The subscale demonstrator tube is machined at the ends.

Figure 13: T700SC carbon fibers $\pm 89.8^\circ$ are temporarily wound over each full $\pm 25^\circ$ TeXtreme® layer, to achieve additional fiber compaction.

Figure 14: Winding of demonstrator tube 13.

Figure 15: Finished demonstrator tube 13.

6 RTM WITH *HoMS*

SICOMP experienced problems in the CHATT project to manufacture 2 mm thick plates from TeXtreme®/epoxy using vacuum infusion and RTM. Mould filling took 5 times longer than when using conventional roving materials. *HoMS* applies to many forms of manufacture of thermoset

composites using un-impregnated spread tow fiber materials with low permeability in the thickness direction including wet filament winding, vacuum infusion, RTM, pultrusion etc. *HoMS* can be used for the following purposes:

- Wet filament winding of spread tow structures, with low void content.
- Vacuum infusion and RTM of spread tow structures, with normal mould filling times.

It was hence decided to use the *HoMS* principle when 10 mm thick plates were manufactured. A 1000x1000x10 mm hybrid (spread tow/roving) plate was vacuum infused from quasi-isotropic carbon (10% TeXtreme®, 90% T700)/epoxy. The T700 is a 0.6 mm thick 0°/90° roving weave. The TeXtreme® is a 0.1 mm thick 0°/90° weave. Both weaves were evenly dispersed in the thickness direction following the 0°/90°/±45° quasi-isotropic layup. The TeXtreme® weave has some minute holes at the 0°/90° crosspoints as supplied. Further holes were created by pre-treating the TeXtreme weave according to *HoMS* before the manufacture. Larger total permeability in the thickness direction was hence achieved. This enabled high quality manufacture of 1000x1000x10 mm plates with normal mold filling times, see Figure 16.

Figure 16: Vacuum infused 1000x1000x10 mm carbon/epoxy plates with TeXtreme®.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Manufacturing process simulations was performed to investigate partly innovative manufacturing procedures, to control the stress state at the significant temperature load defined in the CHATT project. TeXtreme® was introduced as a way of increasing the laminate strength to suppress micro-cracking at -253 °C and also reduce the need for additional liner materials. Processability adjustments were introduced to the TeXtreme® material, which lowered the resulting void content and needed mould filling times. The manufactured subscale demonstrator tubes have successfully been tested in CHATT.

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REFERENCES

- [1] www.chatt.aero.
- [2] http://www.al.com/news/huntsville/index.ssf/2014/08/nasa_boeing_make_major_technol.html.
- [3] K. Olofsson, L. Lewis and R. Dutton, Process simulation of multiple material filament wound pipes, *Proc. ICCM-12, June 1999, Paris*.
- [4] www.oxeon.se.
- [5] E. Marklund, L. Asp, R. Olsson, F. Ohlsson and J. Varna, Experimental investigation and modeling of thin band woven composites, *TexComp-11 conference, September 2013, Leuven*.

- [6] P. Camanho, C. Da´vila, S. Pinho, L. Iannucci and P. Robinson, Prediction of in situ strengths and matrix cracking in composites under transverse tension and in-plane shear, *Composites: Part A* 37 (2006), 165–176.
- [7] S. Sihh, R. Kim, K. Kawabe and S. Tsai, Experimental studies of thin-ply laminated composites, *Composites Science and Technology* 67 (2007), 996–1008.
- [8] H. Saito, H. Takeuchi and I. Kimpara, A study of crack suppression mechanism of thin-ply carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer laminate with mesoscopic numerical simulation, *Journal of Composite Materials* 2014, Vol. 48(17), 2085–2096.